

COMPOSITE RECEIPT AND APPLICATION OF AREAS OF APPLICATION

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Abstract. *This article presents the process of developing a composite using MC-6 type of waste paper and basalt fiber. A study was conducted on improving the quality indicators of waste paper based on basalt fiber and obtaining wrapping paper.*

Keywords: *composite, waste paper, cellulose, composition, basalt fiber, quality indicators.*

Introduction. Over the past 20 years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has made significant progress in pulp and paper production. It should be noted that among dozens of paper and paper products manufacturing enterprises in Uzbekistan, there is a single cardboard paper manufacturing enterprise "TECHNO PRINT" LLC, and now there are more than 10 such large enterprises producing sanitary-hygienic paper. However, the country's demand for pulp and paper is still not being met.

"TECHNO PRINT" LLC was fully operational in 2008. The enterprise is equipped with equipment imported from China. The production process of the enterprise is continuous. The enterprise specializes in the production of thick paper and box products, using MC-5B and MC-6B types of waste paper as raw materials.

It is necessary to restore the physical parameters of waste paper fibers by mechanical and chemical processing, to create good conditions for regenerating the properties of water and fibril structure.

The use of mineral (basalt) fibers in the composition of paper and paper products gives them a set of unique properties that cannot be achieved in materials

based on waste paper fibers. These are high thermal, chemical and biological stability insulating properties, as well as stability to the movement of various types of radiation, including very hard gamma and ultraviolet. The main interesting unique filtration properties are the combination of low aerodynamic resistance with high retention effect of submicron particles.

Traditional types of paper and paper products based on mineral fibers determine their use in various fields of technology, which are suitable or unsatisfactory due to the low stability of waste paper fibers to the aggressive effects of external factors. Examples of successful use of composites such as paper based on mineral fibers can be found in various fields of science and technology. Taking into account the above considerations, we conducted this experiment on MC-6 (old corrugated cardboard or scraps) and basalt (3 different types) fibers of paper.

The technology of mass production from waste paper and basalt fibers for the production of composite paper products includes the following processes:

Separation of waste paper into separate fragments, shredding of fragments, cleaning of waste paper mass in cyclones, sorting and fine cleaning, separation of secondary fiber suspension into fractions depending on size, condensing the mass to 10...15%.

Then, from each of these separately, i.e., by taking equal amounts and mixing them, a composite material was prepared in the laboratory using the wet method. The prepared mass was diluted by 1-1.5%, and a paper sample was cast on the paper casting machine. When the cylinder of the apparatus is slowly raised together with the mesh part, the water mass at the end passes through the mesh to form a wet paper layer. The resulting paper layer together with the mesh is removed and dehydrated in a drying cabinet at 105-110 °C to 75-80% moisture. Then it is pressed in a press until the desired thickness is formed and kept in the press for 30 minutes. At the next stage, the quality indicators of the samples, i.e. breaking length, bending resistance, ash content and water absorption were studied. The following tables show the analysis of the results.

Table 1

Quality indicators of composite paper samples based on basalt fiber (ultrafine) and waste paper

№	Waste paper, %	Basalt fiber, %	Quality indicators			
			Breaking length, mm	Bending strength, H	Ash content, %	Water absorption, %
1	100	-	3700	25	6.80	3.45
2	75	25	2100	15	7.10	3.36
3	50	50	900	3	8.20	2.36
4	-	100	-	-	9.80	2.20

Quality indicators of composite paper samples based on basalt fiber (fine) and waste paper

№	Waste paper, %	Basalt fiber, %	Quality indicators			
			Breaking length, mm	Bending strength, H	Ash content, %	Water absorption, %
1	100	-	3700	25	6.80	3.45
2	75	25	2800	17	7.90	3.81
3	50	50	1600	8	9.60	3.66
4	-	100	-	-	12.12	3.95

Quality indicators of composite paper samples based on basalt fiber (coarse) and pulp

№	Waste paper, %	Basalt fiber, %	Quality indicators			
			Breaking length, mm	Bending strength, H	Ash content, %	Water absorption, %
7	100	-	3700	25	6.80	3.45
8	75	25	1500	13	8.20	4.92
9	50	50	800	2	10.12	4.10
10	-	100	-	-	14.12	5.95

Conclusion. As can be seen from the tables, three different types of basalt fiber samples and MS-6 composite paper samples obtained on the basis of different waste paper were studied and compared for breaking length, bending resistance, ash content and water absorbency indicators. From the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that it is appropriate to use very fine and fine types of basalt fiber, because the amount of ash and the degree of elasticity are smaller than those of coarse fiber.

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